

Synthesis of *N*-Allyl-2-oxocycloalkanecarbothioamides, Functionalised Organic Intermediates *via* Enamines

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Cyclopent-1-enylmorpholine (1a)/pyrrolidine (1b) and cyclohex-1-enylpyrrolidine (1c)/aniline (1d) with allyl isothiocyanate furnish *N*-allyl-2-oxo-cyclopentane- and *N*-allyl-2-oxocyclohexanecarbothioamides (3, *n*=3/4), respectively after hydrolysis of the product mixture.

THE carbothioamide intermediates (2, R=alkyl, aryl, acyl and aroyl), formed as 1 : 1 adducts in the reactions of enamines (1) and isothiocyanates through the interaction of enamine β -carbon and isothiocyanato carbon are useful in the synthesis of a variety of heterocyclic systems^{1,2}. The presence of allyl group in such compounds (2, R=allyl) would be of enhanced synthetic consequence. Earlier, we found that allyl isothiocyanate, contrary to literature reports^{1,2}, reacts at $-\text{NH}_2$ and not at enamine β -carbon of ethyl β -aminocrotonate³. Here, we report that more reactive enamines, *viz.* cycloalk-1-enylamines (1) in their reactions with allyl isothiocyanate reacts at enamine β -carbon to provide *N*-allyl-2-oxocycloalkanecarbothioamides (3) through the hydrolysis of initially formed adduct (2, R=allyl).

Cyclopent-1-enylmorpholine (1a) with allyl isothiocyanate at room temperature gives a product mixture consisting of three components, A, R_f 0.70; B, R_f 0.60 and C, R_f 0.30 (CHCl_3 , EtOH, 95 : 5). The component A during chromatography changed to the component B. The component B obtained as a dark brown liquid in its mass spectrum shows the parent ion peak $M^+ m/z$ 183 (M.F. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{NOS}$). Its pmr spectrum shows the signals at δ 1.75-2.8 (m, 6H) and 3.5-3.9 (m, 1H) (monosubstituted cyclopentanone ring H), 4.3 (d, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.0-6.2 (m, 3H, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$) and 8.85 (1H, NH exchangeable with D_2O) and the ir bands appear at 3250 (NH) and 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O). On the basis of these spectral data, it has been assigned the structure *N*-allyl-2-oxocyclopentanecarbothioamide (3, *n*=3). Component C has been found to be identical (R_f and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample of *N*-allyl-morpholine-1-carbothioamide (4)⁴.

It was argued that component A might be *N*-allyl-2-(1-morpholinyl)-1-cyclopentene-1-carbothioamide (2a, R=allyl) which on chromatography hydrolysed to (3, *n*=3). Alternatively, the crude product mixture was hydrolysed with 4 *N* HCl and after work-up it consisted of only (3, *n*=3) and (4).

Similarly, the reactions of cyclopent-1-enylpyrrolidine (1b) and cyclohex-1-enylpyrrolidine (1c)

with allyl isothiocyanate furnished (3, *n*=3) and (3, *n*=4), respectively along with *N*-allyl-pyrrolidine-carbothioamide (5). Cyclohex-1-enylaniline (1d) with allyl isothiocyanate provided (3, *n*=4) and *N*-phenyl-*N*-allyl thiourea (6).

Hence, unlike ethyl β -aminocrotonate, cycloalk-1-enylamines (1) react with allyl isothiocyanate at enamine β -carbon, and the adducts (2, R=allyl) thus formed hydrolyse to the corresponding *N*-allyl-2-oxocycloalkanecarbothioamide derivatives (3) which constitute functionalised organic intermediates of potential synthetic utility. The *N*-allyl carbothioamide derivatives (4, 5 and 6) of amines might be formed from the free amine present as an impurity in the enamine.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillaries and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on Tesla BS 487C 80MHz instrument using TMS as internal standard. Ir spectra were recorded with CZ specord-7 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were run on Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer RMU-60D instrument. For tlc, plates coated with silica gel G were run in chloroform and the spots were developed in an iodine chamber.

Reaction of cyclopent-1-enylmorpholine (1a) with allyl isothiocyanate: (i) A mixture of cyclopent-1-enylmorpholine (1.53 g, 0.01 mol) and allyl isothiocyanate (0.99 g, 0.01 mol) was stirred at room temperature under anhydrous condition. The progress of the reaction was monitored through tlc, and completed after 1 h. The reaction mixture consisted of three components A, R_f 0.70; B, R_f 0.60 and C, R_f 0.30. (CHCl_3 , EtOH, 95 : 5). The product mixture was chromatographed over neutral alumina using benzene as eluent and component A could not be isolated. Component B, *N*-allyl-2-oxocyclopentanecarbothioamide (3 *n*=3) was isolated as a dark brown liquid (85)%. Component C, *N*-allyl-morpholine-1-carbothioamide (4), m.p. 53-54°, was found to be identical with an authentic sample of (4)⁴.

(ii) In a separate reaction, the solution of the crude product mixture in 4 *N* HCl, was heated on a water bath. The reaction was monitored by tlc of aliquot portions of the reaction mixture drawn at regular intervals for the disappearance of component A which took 1 h. The reaction mixture was basified with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent distilled off and the residue consisted of *N*-allyl-2-oxo-cyclopentanecarbothioamide (3, $n=3$), (90%) and *N*-allyl morpholine-1-carbothioamide (4) which were isolated by column chromatography.

The following reactions were performed in a similar manner and the product mixtures were hydrolysed. The products were isolated by column chromatography over neutral alumina using benzene as eluent.

Reaction of cyclopent-1-enylpyrrolidine (1b) and allyl isothiocyanate: The reaction gives (i) *N*-allyl-2-oxocyclopentanecarbothioamide (3, $n=3$) (85%), and (ii) *N*-allyl-pyrrolidine-1-carbothioamide (4), m.p. 61-2° (Found: N, 5.52. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 16.46%); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 2.05 (4H, m) and 3.66 (4H, m) (Pyrrolidine H), 4.21 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.05 (3H, m, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$).

Reaction of cyclohex-1-enylpyrrolidine (1c) and allyl isothiocyanate: The reaction gives (i) *N*-allyl-2-oxocyclohexanecarbothioamide (3, $n=4$) (90%), a dark brown semi-solid; ν_{max} 3350, 2925, 1705, 1660, 1640, 1600, 1560, 1370, 1350, 1330, 1290 cm^{-1} , $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.15-2.5 and 2.7 (9H, cyclohexanone H), 4.22 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.0-6.2 (3H, m, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 9.6 (1H, NH, exchangeable with D_2O); M^+m/z 197 (M.F. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{NOS}$), and (ii) *N*-allyl-pyrrolidine-1-carbothioamide (5).

Reaction of cyclohex-1-enylaniline (1d) and allyl isothiocyanate: The reaction gives (i) *N*-allyl-2-oxocyclohexanecarbothioamide (3, $n=4$) (80%), and (ii) *N*-phenyl-*N*-allyl thiourea (6).

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